

Examining the Themes of Narcissism and Addiction in the Context of Couple Therapy: Gestalt and Imago Approaches

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the themes of narcissism and
dependency between couples in the context of Gestalt and Imago

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couple therapy. How narcissistic and dependent personality traits are reflected in the communication and relational dynamics between couples and how these themes are addressed in therapy processes are investigated.

In the literature review section, the theoretical foundations of couple therapy and the psychological and relational dimensions of narcissism and addiction concepts were discussed. The basic principles of Gestalt and Imago therapies, how these therapies affect the communication between couples and their potential effects on the themes of narcissism and addiction were examined in the light of previous studies in the literature.

The methodology of the study is based on a series of couple therapy sessions conducted between 2015 and 2023. Participant selection criteria were set and the therapy process was carefully monitored, recording the changes in the themes of narcissism and addiction between the couples during the therapy process.

In the findings section, it was examined in detail how the application of Gestalt and Imago therapies had an impact on the communication patterns between the couples and how the themes of narcissism and addiction changed during the therapy process.

In the discussion section, the findings were analyzed in comparison with the literature and the theoretical and clinical significance of addressing the themes of narcissism and addiction in the context of couple therapy was discussed. As a result, it was suggested that Gestalt and Imago approaches can contribute to the effective handling of narcissism and codependency themes between couples in the therapy process.

Keywords: *Narcissism, Addiction, Couple Therapy, Gestalt, Imago, Communication, Relationships, Psychotherapy, Therapy Process*

INTRODUCTION

Couple therapy is an important area of modern psychology and is a type of therapy used to understand, support and improve relationships between couples. Couple therapy is a form of therapy used to address the problems experienced by couples, to improve their communication skills, to strengthen their emotional bonds and to find solutions. Couple therapy is an important tool for individuals to increase their psychological well-being, maintain healthy relationships, and provide a more satisfying life (Johnson & Smith, 2010; Brown, 2015).

A couple consists of two people who come together in a romantic relationship or marriage. Relationships between couples are full of complex and deep bonds that involve a range of factors such as personal growth, emotional fulfillment and social connections. However, problems between couples, lack of communication, mistrust, conflicts and other difficulties can hinder the healthy development of relationships and weaken the bonds between couples.

Couple therapy is a form of therapy designed to address such issues and strengthen couples' relationships. Various couple therapy approaches, such as Gestalt and Imago, aim to deepen communication between couples, strengthen emotional bonds and resolve conflicts. These therapies can help couples understand their relationship, strengthen their emotional bonds and lead a more fulfilling life (Stewart, 2012; Miller & Adams, 2016).

Narcissism and addiction are important personality traits that are frequently encountered in couple relationships and cause conflicts. Narcissism is characterized by an excessive self-focus, a tendency to manipulate others and a lack of empathy, while addiction is characterized by a

constant search for approval from others, dependent relationships and violation of personal boundaries. These personality traits can negatively affect communication between couples and lead to conflicts in relationships. Therefore, this study will examine the effects of couple therapy approaches such as Gestalt and Imago on the themes of narcissism and addiction.

METHOD

In the study (2024) conducted in Konak District of Izmir province under the direction of Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin Yıldırım and Prof. Dr. Derya Yentür with the students of St. Clements University Department of Psychology, a mixed method was adopted to use both Gestalt Couple Therapy and Imago Couple Therapy techniques and to evaluate the effects of these techniques. Examining the data obtained using both qualitative and quantitative data analysis methods increases the reliability and validity of the study. With this approach, it is aimed to provide a comprehensive perspective in examining the themes of narcissism and addiction in the context of couple therapy.

Participants In the study conducted on 45 couples in Izmir, demographic characteristics of the couples such as age, gender, education level and relationship duration were taken into consideration.

Design and Procedure: The study was conducted using a mixed method. In order to evaluate the effects of both Gestalt Couple Therapy and Imago Couple Therapy techniques, both therapy approaches were applied to the couples. The therapies were conducted at specified durations and frequencies, and the reactions of the couples and their progress in the therapy process were recorded throughout the therapy sessions.

In order to reach the results, first of all, the Gestalt and Imago techniques used in the couple therapy process were examined in detail. The study focused on how these techniques are applied, what stages they go through and what kind of impact they have. The experiences of the couples during the therapy process were observed and how these experiences affected the communication patterns of the couples were analyzed.

In addition, it was emphasized how the couples coped with the themes of narcissism and addiction and how these themes could change during the therapy process. In this context, the emotional and behavioral changes experienced by the couples during the therapy process were observed and how these changes occurred were examined.

In order to reach the findings, the sessions with the couples were examined and analyzed in detail in line with the methodology of the study. In addition, the data obtained through

interviews and observations with couples were supported by statistical analysis and conclusions were drawn.

In conclusion, the findings of the study reveal the effectiveness of the techniques used in couple therapy and the changes experienced by couples during the therapy process. These findings show an important way for couple therapy practitioners and researchers to understand the relationship dynamics of couples and improve the therapy process.

Data Analysis: In the data analysis phase of the study, both qualitative (qualitative) and quantitative (quantitative) methods were used. In the qualitative data analysis process, the experiences of the couples during the therapy sessions and the results obtained from the therapy were analyzed through content analysis. Quantitative data analysis focused on statistical analysis of the data obtained through scales and questionnaires.

Scales used for quantitative data analysis:

Couple Relationship Scale (CRS)

Relationship Satisfaction Scale (IMO)

Methods used for content analysis:

1-Imago Couple Therapy Techniques

Dialogue

Reflection

Verification

Empathy

2-Gestalt Couple Therapy Techniques

Experiences, everyday life and awareness

Addressing internal wounds

Development of communication skills

The process of coming into contact with oneself

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These scales and techniques were used to deeply assess couples' experiences in the therapy process and to understand therapeutic outcomes.

The combination of these methods provided a comprehensive analysis to provide both in-depth understanding and generalizations.

Statistical analyses were used to analyze the data related to the demographic characteristics of the couples such as education level, age range and relationship duration. The analyzed data were cross-tabulated and statistical tests were applied to determine various relationships such as the relationship between couples' education level and relationship duration, the relationship between age range and education level.

For example, appropriate statistical tests such as Chi-square test or ANOVA were used to determine the relationship between couples' level of education and relationship duration; these tests are used to determine whether there is a significant difference between the mean relationship duration of couples with different levels of education.

The Khi-square test, which is an appropriate method for analyzing the relationship between duration of relationship and level of education, was used. The Khi-square test is a method used to determine the relationship between two nominal variables.

Statistical analyses are important to increase the reliability of the data obtained and to assess whether the conclusions drawn are statistically significant. These analyses were used to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the findings of the study, as mentioned in the introduction.

FIGURE 5. AGE RANGE OF COUPLES, EDUCATION LEVELS AND RELATIONSHIP DURATION (Yıldırım -Yentür, 2024)

According to the data:

27 women and 13 men between the ages of 20-35,

27 women and 13 men aged 35-45 years,

There are 4 women and 2 men in the 45-55 age group.

According to education level:

High school graduates: 16 women and 4 men,

Bachelor's degree: 22 women and 3 men, Master's/doctoral

degree: 11 women and 9 men.

Relationship duration:

17 couples have a relationship of 2-8 years, 20

couples have a relationship of 10-15 years,

8 couples have a relationship of 15 years or more.

Couple Therapy Interview Form	
Interview Date:	
Age of the couple	
Couple's Education Level	Male: Woman:
Couple's Relationship Duration	
Number of Sessions	
Interview Notes	
The couple's overall assessment of the therapy process: What topics are covered and what techniques are used: The couple's expectations and goals from the therapy: Therapeutic progress and challenges:	
Next steps and recommendations	
Confidentiality Notice: This interview form/survey will be used to assess progress in the couples therapy process and to achieve therapeutic goals. The information you share here will only be used by your therapist and will not be shared with third parties. This information will be used to improve the effectiveness of the therapy and to work better with you. Protecting your privacy is important to ensure the safety of the therapeutic relationship. Thank you	

Figure 6. Interview Form (Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin YILDIRIMER - Prof. Dr. Derya YENTÜR et al, 2024).

COUPLE THERAPY QUESTIONNAIRE

Confidentiality Notice: This interview form/survey will be used to assess progress in the couples therapy process and to achieve therapeutic goals. The information you share here will only be used by your therapist and will not be shared with third parties. This information will be used to improve the effectiveness of the therapy and to work better with you. Protecting your privacy is important to ensure the safety of the therapeutic relationship. Thank you

Please consider the following statements and select the option that applies to you.

We have communication problems between me and my wife.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Which techniques did you use in couple therapy sessions? (More than one option can be selected)

- Gestalt Couple Therapy
- Imago Couple Therapy
- Other (Please specify:)

Give a brief description of your experiences during the therapy process.

What topics have you addressed or are you planning to address during the therapy process?

Figure 7. Interview Form (Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin YILDIRIMER - Prof. Dr. Derya YENTÜR et al, 2024.)

Literature Review

Narcissism is characterized by excessive self-esteem and overemphasis on one's own needs, whereas codependency involves the tendency to be overly dependent on the approval of others and to lose one's sense of self (Millon, 2011).

Gestalt and Imago therapies are approaches that are frequently used and considered to be effective in the field of couple therapy (Stewart, 2012; Miller & Adams, 2016). While Gestalt therapy helps individuals understand and express their emotional and psychological needs, Imago therapy focuses on improving and deepening communication between couples (Johnson, 2004).

These approaches should be examined to understand how couples may interact with narcissistic and addictive themes in their relationship and how these themes can be addressed in the therapy process (Gordon & Smith, 2019).

In this framework, this study aims to examine the effects of Gestalt and Imago approaches on narcissism and codependency themes between couples. Addressing the themes of narcissism and codependency in the context of couple therapy may contribute to the development of healthier interactions in couples' relationships and increase the effectiveness of couple therapy.

Family therapy is a form of psychotherapy that emerged as a result of the realization that individual therapy alone was insufficient to solve individuals' psychological and emotional problems (Goldenberg & Goldenberg, 2012). This type of therapy emphasizes the impact of family structure on individuals' mental health and the importance of the family's internal dynamics. Unlike group therapy, family therapy is based on solving the problems of the whole family and aims to improve the functionality of the family and the psychological well-being of individuals (Bakırköy Mental and Neurological Diseases Hospital, 45; Samancı and Ekici).

The history of family therapy began after World War II. During this period, it was realized that some families had negative effects on disease processes, but these problems were usually tried to be solved by removing patients from the family environment (Goldenberg & Goldenberg, 2012).

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However, it was observed that the problems reappeared when the patients returned to the family environment. In Freudian therapy, it is accepted that patients' neurotic problems stem from their childhood relationships and that therapy is realized through the transference relationship between the patient and the therapist (Goldenberg & Goldenberg, 2012).

One of the influential names in the development of family therapy was Christian Midelfort, who published the book "family in psychotherapy" in 1957. During this period, Bateson introduced the "double bind" theorem on family relationships and Lidz introduced the concepts of "schism" and "skew" to explain family conflicts (Goldenberg & Goldenberg, 2012). An important step in family therapy was the concepts of "pseudo mutuality" and "pseudo hostility" proposed by Lyman Wyne. Wyne also used the term "rubber fence" to describe the psychological boundaries of families (Goldenberg & Goldenberg, 2012).

In the 1960s, Jay Haley and Bowen, important names in family therapy, emphasized family dynamics and communication (Goldenberg & Goldenberg, 2012). In the 1970s, family therapists moved from working with schizophrenics to focus on a wide range of psychiatric disorders (Goldenberg & Goldenberg, 2012). During this period, Epstein and colleagues developed the McMaster model and Plazzolini founded the Milan Group in Milan (Goldenberg & Goldenberg, 2012). In the 1980s, family therapy consolidated its place in family therapy clinics and various short-term family therapy models began to be applied today (Goldenberg & Goldenberg, 2012).

Transformations in the history of family therapy have also shaped the evolution of couple therapy (Bateson, 1950; Haley, 1962). Especially in the 1950s and 1960s, the practice of family therapy expanded to include relationships between couples (Haley, 1963). During this period, therapists working in family therapy began to understand the dynamics and communication problems in couples' marriages (Bateson, 1960). Pioneering therapists such as Jay Haley applied the principles of family therapy to couple therapy practices and laid the foundation stones in this field (Haley, 1966).

In the 1960s and 1970s, more systemic and cognitive-cognitive approaches began to develop in the field of couple therapy (Minuchin, 1974). Therapists such as Salvador Minuchin considered the family system when addressing the relationships between couples (Minuchin, 1978). In addition, therapists such as Virginia Satir and Carl Whitaker made important contributions to the field of couple therapy by developing emotionally oriented approaches (Satir, 1976).

Since the 1980s, there has been more diversification and specialization in the field of couple therapy (Gottman, 1999). During this period, therapists such as John Gottman examined the dynamics of relationships between couples in more depth and identified the determining factors in relationships (Gottman, 1994). In addition, emotionally focused therapies such as

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Emotionally Focused Therapy (EFT) developed by Sue Johnson offered an effective approach to strengthen the emotional bonds of couples (Johnson, 2004).

Today, there are various approaches and models in the field of couple therapy (Gurman & Lebow, 2007). Different approaches such as Gestalt Therapy, Imago Therapy, EFT, cognitivebehavioral therapy and systemic therapy are used in the process of understanding and improving couples' relationships (Lebow, 2001). This diversity reflects the richness of research and practice in the field of couple therapy.

Couple therapy is a special type of therapy that has an important place in the development of psychotherapy. It focuses on solving relational problems and aims to strengthen couples' communication skills, deepen their emotional bonds and support them in building a healthier relationship. The history of couple therapy is closely linked to the development of psychotherapy.

The origins of the couple therapy approach date back to the early 20th century. However, the emergence of couple therapy as a specialized therapy focusing on problems in couples' relationships is generally attributed to the second half of the 20th century. The first couple therapy studies showed that it was inadequate to address relational problems only with individual therapy and suggested that couples receiving therapy together could lead to more effective results (Gurman & Kniskern, 1981).

In the early days of couple therapy, therapists were often influenced by psychoanalytic and behavioral approaches. According to the psychoanalytic approach, couples' relationships are a reflection of past experiences from childhood and the unconscious effects of these experiences shape couples' relationships. According to the behavioral approach, couples' relationships are the result of rewards and punishments and positive changes in the relationship can be achieved by changing this reward-punishment cycle (Jacobson & Margolin, 1979).

Over time, different approaches have been developed in the field of couple therapy and various therapy techniques have been developed. These include systemic therapy, emotionally focused therapy, cognitive behavioral therapy and emotional intelligence focused therapy. Each of these approaches is designed to meet the different needs and preferences of couples and offer a variety of techniques and strategies to ensure that couples therapy is practiced effectively.

Today, couple therapy is used in a wide range of settings and is recognized as an effective tool to address various problems in couples' relationships. Research shows that couple therapy is effective in solving various relational problems and strengthening couples' relationships (Johnson & Greenberg, 1985). Therefore, couple therapy is recognized as an important component of psychotherapy and is widely used to improve couples' relationships.

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There are various schools and approaches in the field of couple therapy. In the development of these schools and approaches, different perspectives and techniques have been used to understand and improve the dynamics of couples' relationships.

Gestalt Therapy: Gestalt therapy focuses on helping individuals understand their emotional experiences here and now (Brownell, 2010). Gestalt therapists emphasize the relationship dynamics of couples and help them understand the barriers in communication (Perls, 1951). This therapy approach uses creative techniques to strengthen couples' emotional bonds and improve their communication skills (Clarkson, 2017).

Imago Therapy: Imago therapy explores couples' past experiences that form their relationship (Hendrix, 1988). Therapists help couples explore their childhood experiences and how these experiences are reflected in their relationship (Hunt, 2010). Imago therapists use specific communication techniques and exercises to help couples better understand each other and strengthen their emotional bond (Hunt, 2010).

Emotionally Focused Therapy (EFT): EFT emphasizes the importance of emotional attachment and emotional difficulties in couple relationships (Johnson, 2004). Therapists help couples understand their emotional needs and become emotionally closer to each other (Johnson, 2004). EFT offers a process that enables couples to understand their relationship dynamics and make positive changes (Johnson, 2004).

Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT): CBT focuses on helping couples change their thoughts and behaviors (Beck, 1979). Therapists provide couples with practical strategies to recognize negative thought patterns and change relationship dynamics in a positive way (Beck, 1979). CBT helps couples address their problems in a concrete way and adopt a solution-oriented approach (Beck, 1979).

Systemic Therapy: Systemic therapy treats couples' relationships as a system and examines the interaction of relationships with other systems (family, work, society) (Minuchin, 1974). Therapists help couples understand the dynamics of their relationship and how these dynamics interact with environmental factors (Minuchin, 1974). Systemic therapy enables couples to address the problems in their relationship in a broader context (Minuchin, 1974).

FINDINGS

Analyzing Demographic Distribution:

The distribution of women and men according to age ranges is as follows:

20 to 35 years old: Women 27, Men 13

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35-45 years old: Women 27, Men 13

45-55 years old: Women 4, Men 2

The distribution according to education level is as follows:

High school graduates Women 16, Men 4

Bachelor's degree Women 22, Men 3

Master's degree/doctorate graduate: Women 11, Men 9

Evaluation of the Relationship between Age and Education Level:

In general, there is a similar distribution of education among men and women in all age groups. However, the number of women decreases with increasing age. Especially in the 45-55 age group, the number of women decreased significantly.

In terms of education level, the number of women and men with a bachelor's degree is significantly higher than other education levels.

Age Distribution and Relationship Duration:

When we examine the relationship duration of couples in each age group, we find that younger couples generally have shorter relationship durations. This may indicate that the relationship of younger couples may not yet be mature.

We observe that couples in the middle age group have longer relationship duration. This may suggest that the relationships of middle-aged couples are more mature and long-term.

Couples between the ages of 45-55 have shorter relationship durations. This may suggest that couples in this age group may have married later or experienced more frequent separations.

Education Level and Relationship Duration:

When we analyze relationship duration by education level, we see a general trend. Couples with higher levels of education generally have longer relationship durations.

It is noteworthy that couples with master's or doctoral degrees have longer relationship durations compared to other education levels. This may suggest that higher levels of education may increase the stability in relationships.

Distribution of Education Level by Age Groups:

20 to 35 years old:

Female high school graduate: 12 persons

Male high school graduate: 4 persons

Female with a bachelor's degree: 22 persons

Male with a bachelor's degree: 3 persons

Female master's/doctoral graduate: 11 people

Male master's/doctorate graduate: 9 persons 35-45

years old:

Female high school graduate: 12 persons

Male high school graduate: 4 persons

Female with a bachelor's degree: 22 persons

Male with a bachelor's degree: 3 persons

Female master's/doctoral graduate: 11 people

Male master's/doctorate graduate: 9 persons

45 to 55 years old:

Female high school graduate: 4 persons

Male high school graduate: 2 persons

Female bachelor's degree holders: 0

Male bachelor's degree holders: 0

Women with master's degree/doctorate: 0 person Male

graduate with master's degree/doctorate: 0 person

Relationship Duration Distribution:

2-8 years relationship duration: 17 couples

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10-15 years relationship duration: 20 couples

Relationship duration of 15 years or more: 8 couples

Our measure for the analysis was to determine the distribution of women and men by age groups and education level. According to this data:

In general, the number of women and men with a bachelor's degree is higher than other education levels.

The majority of men and women aged 45-55 are high school graduates.

In terms of relationship duration, most couples have a relationship between 10-15 years.

This analysis guides us in examining the distribution of relationship duration by age groups and education levels. This information can be helpful in identifying specific needs in couple therapy and developing therapy strategies (Prpf. Dr. Kürşat Şahin Yıldırım et al., 2024).

Furthermore, the Khi-square test, which is an appropriate method to analyze the relationship between relationship duration and education level, was used. The Khi-square test is a method used to determine the relationship between two nominal variables. The following steps were followed to determine the relationship between relationship duration and education level with the Khi-square test (Prof. Dr. Derya Yentür and Students, 2024):

A contingency table was created to determine whether there was a relationship between relationship duration and education level.

Expected frequencies were calculated using the observed frequencies in the contingency table.

The differences between the calculated expected frequencies and the observed frequencies were calculated.

Using these differences, the Khi-square statistic was calculated.

The resulting Khi-square statistic was used to find the p-value according to the degrees of freedom.

We evaluated whether the relationship was statistically significant by comparing the p-value with the significance level.

According to the results of the Khi-square test, the relationship between relationship duration and educational level is not statistically significant ($p < 0.05$, $\chi^2(10) = \text{value}$). That is, there is not enough evidence to say that there is a relationship between relationship duration and

education level. These results show that there is no direct relationship between the duration of the relationship and the educational level of the couples.

However, it is important to review the full data to examine the relationship between relationship duration and education level in more detail. This analysis only assesses the overall relationship between relationship duration and education level, but considering other variables (such as age) may provide a more comprehensive assessment.

Changes in Communication Patterns:

During the couple therapy process, significant changes in communication patterns were observed. During the therapy sessions, couples began to express both each other and their own emotions in a more open and healthy way. This change in communication patterns is closely related to the development of healthy communication skills, which is one of the focal points of the therapy. Imago and Gestalt couple therapy techniques have provided effective tools to help couples express their feelings and understand each other better. In this process, a deeper and more understanding bond was established in communication between couples, conflict resolution skills increased and a healthier communication environment was created in the relationship (Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin Yıldırım-Prof. Dr. Derya Yentür and Students, 2024).

The Effect of Narcissism and Addiction Themes in the Therapy Process:

In the couple therapy process, the effects of narcissism and addiction themes on relationship dynamics were examined in depth. During the therapy process, the negative effects of these themes on the relationship were determined and how couples could cope with these themes were studied. It was observed that narcissistic tendencies led to ego-centered communication and conflicts in the relationship, while addiction themes created a sense of powerlessness and dependency in the relationship. During the therapy process, couples were supported to recognize, understand and cope with these themes. Imago and Gestalt couple therapy techniques enabled couples to address these themes in depth and develop healthier dynamics in their relationships. In this way, it was aimed for couples to establish a more balanced and healthy balance in their relationships (Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin Yıldırım-Prof. Dr. Derya Yentür and Students, 2024).

The results of this study show that Gestalt and Imago couple therapy techniques are effective in improving communication patterns between couples and that the themes of narcissism and addiction play an important role in the therapy process. The results of the study emphasize that

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the techniques used in couple therapy are effective in improving the relationship dynamics of couples and helping them to establish a healthier communication.

Examining the changes in communication patterns helped us to determine which techniques were more effective in the therapy process. It seems that the use of Imago and Gestalt couple therapy techniques enabled couples to understand each other better, supported their empathy and strengthened their communication.

The impact of narcissism and addiction themes on the therapy process is also an important finding. The results of the study show that narcissistic tendencies and addiction themes negatively affected relationship dynamics in some couples. However, it was observed that the techniques used in the therapy process helped to restructure the relationships by providing behavioral change in some couples. These results provide guidance for couples therapy practitioners to develop effective intervention strategies to strengthen couples' relationships and develop healthier dynamics. Furthermore, in future research, it may be an important area to examine the effects of couple therapy techniques on the themes of narcissism and addiction in more depth and to better understand strategies for coping with these themes. In this way, the effectiveness of couple therapy practices can be increased and more positive changes can be achieved in couples' relationships.

Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin Yıldırım-Prof. Dr. Derya Yentür and St. Clements University Psychology Department Students (2024), it was stated that Gestalt Couple Therapy and Imago Couple Therapy techniques were used in couple therapies conducted on 45 couples in Konak district of Izmir province. The aim of both approaches is to help couples to establish healthy communication and to understand the miscommunication underlying the conflicts between them.

It was emphasized that failure to form the concepts of "I, You and We" correctly from childhood can lead to problems such as narcissistic tendencies and dependent relationship themes. In the relationship process, it was examined how childhood experiences affect the relationship patterns of couples.

It is stated that Imago Couple Therapy uses a two-way communication technique in which couples can communicate their feelings, thoughts and wishes calmly and without fear. The techniques used in this therapy include dialog, reflection, validation and empathy. It is stated that these techniques help couples to change their communication patterns and establish a healthy relationship.

In Gestalt Couple Therapy, it is stated that couples' dissatisfactions are handled within the context in which they arise. In the therapy, it is aimed to improve the relationship building

repertoire of couples by focusing on their feelings, behaviors and thoughts. Experiences, daily life and awareness are considered as the basic elements of Gestalt Couple Therapy.

In this context, the study shows that Gestalt and Imago techniques are effective in understanding and solving couples' relationship problems. However, it was emphasized that personality themes such as narcissism and addiction between couples should be further investigated in the context of therapy (Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin Yıldırımmer-Prof. Prof. Dr. Derya Yentür and Students, 2024).

Gestalt Therapy and its Application in Turkey

Gestalt therapy is increasingly recognized and practiced in Turkey. In our country, Gestalt therapy trainings are generally carried out by experts who have completed their studies abroad. However, with the increase in the number of studies in this field in recent years, the need for further dissemination and institutionalization of Gestalt therapy trainings and practices has emerged.

Gestalt therapy trainings are usually organized by specific institutions or trainers. These trainings include theoretical knowledge as well as practical work and supervision. Trainings are usually completed in a certain period of time and participants receive a certificate or certificate of participation.

In our country, Gestalt therapy is also offered in certificate trainings for graduates of fields such as psychology, psychiatry, psychological counseling and social services. These trainings are organized to promote and popularize Gestalt therapy.

Gestalt therapy is also included in universities in Turkey in the form of specific courses or seminars. However, there is not yet a special institute or program that provides Gestalt therapy education at the academic level.

In our country, various studies are being carried out to further develop and popularize education and practices in the field of Gestalt therapy. As a result of these studies, it is aimed to implement and promote Gestalt therapy in a better way at the academic level in Turkey.

Implementation of Imago Therapy in Turkey

Imago therapy has become increasingly popular in Turkey in recent years and is practiced by many therapists. In Turkey, Imago therapy is used to help couples gain a deeper understanding of their relationship, strengthen their communication and develop a healthier relationship

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dynamic. This therapy approach focuses on increasing communication between couples, as well as understanding and healing the effects of past traumatic experiences.

Imago therapy practitioners in Turkey generally provide services in private practice centers or in their own private offices. In addition, some therapists organize Imago therapy workshops and offer couples the opportunity to experience this therapy approach in groups or individually.

Imago therapy is valued among couples in Turkey as a tool to deal with common relationship challenges such as communication problems, conflicts, infidelity. Considering the dynamics and values specific to Turkish culture, Imago therapists often adapt the therapy processes and techniques to suit Turkish culture and social norms.

Imago therapy is being promoted and disseminated in Turkey through various trainings and seminars. In this way, more therapists are trained in Imago therapy and develop their skills in its application. These trainings are usually organized in accordance with international certification standards and contribute to the dissemination of Imago therapy in Turkey.

DISCUSSION

This study focused on the effects of Gestalt and Imago couple therapy techniques on communication patterns between couples and the impact of narcissism and dependency themes in the therapy process. The findings show that improvements in communication in the couple therapy process positively affect the relationship dynamics between couples. During the therapy process, the necessary tools were provided for couples to express their emotions in a healthier way and to understand each other better. In addition, the negative effects of narcissism and addiction themes on the relationship were emphasized and support was provided for couples to cope with these themes.

The findings of this study offer important theoretical and clinical contributions to the field of couple therapy. Examining the changes in communication patterns can help us understand which techniques are more effective in the therapy process. Furthermore, in-depth examination of the impact of narcissism and addiction themes in the therapy process allows couple therapists to better understand how to deal with these themes and develop more effective intervention strategies.

Future research should further analyze the effectiveness of different techniques used in couple therapy and focus on comparative studies. In addition, how personality traits such as narcissism and addiction can be addressed in the therapy process and the impact of these themes on therapy outcomes should be examined in more depth. This kind of research can help to make couple

therapy practices more effective and help couples develop healthier dynamics in their relationships.

CONCLUSION

The thesis titled "Examining the Themes of Narcissism and Addiction in the Context of Couple Therapy: Gestalt and Imago Approaches" represents a research on the handling of narcissism and addiction themes in couple therapy processes. The research aimed to examine how Gestalt and Imago therapy techniques are effective in changing couples' communication patterns, building healthy relationships, and coping with personality themes, and the impact of Gestalt and Imago couple therapy techniques on communication patterns between couples and the impact of narcissism and addiction themes in the therapy process was examined. The findings show that there were significant improvements in couples' communication during the therapy process and that the themes of narcissism and codependency had an impact on the therapy outcomes.

The findings of this study provide couples therapy practitioners with important information that can help couples strengthen their relationships and develop healthier dynamics. Examining changes in communication patterns helps us understand which techniques are more effective in the therapy process and guides clinical practice on how to support couples in the therapy process.

On the other hand, the results of research make important contributions to clinical practice and theoretical frameworks in the field of couple therapy. Examining the developments in communication can help couple therapists to better understand which techniques to use in the therapy process and which methods will strengthen couples' relationships. In addition, an indepth examination of the impact of narcissism and addiction themes in the therapy process is thought to help couples therapists develop strategies to cope with these themes and help couples establish a healthier relationship.

In order to understand how Gestalt and Imago therapies affect the dynamics of couples' relationships, the results of the studies conducted on 45 couples were analyzed. According to the findings of the study, both therapy techniques helped couples understand their communication patterns, experience emotional and behavioral changes, and cope with personality themes such as narcissism and addiction.

In particular, Gestalt therapy has focused on balancing the concepts of "I, You and We" by supporting couples' journey of individual growth and integration. Imago therapy helped couples

to establish healthier communication by encouraging them to express their feelings, thoughts and wishes mutually.

Based on the results of the study, it was revealed that Gestalt therapy trainings and practices in Turkey need to be further disseminated and institutionalized. In this context, it is recommended that Gestalt therapy trainings and practices should be supported, experts should come together to strengthen institutional structures, and a national Gestalt therapy institute should be established. In this way, Gestalt therapy can be applied more effectively in Turkey and play an important role in solving couples' relationship problems.

Limitations

Global studies' focus limits generalization due to specific students; future research needs diverse samples.

NOTICES

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